

Local Government in India

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Asha Sarangi and Lipika Ravichandran

Centre for Political Studies
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Partners

eurac
research

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism
University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in India is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Jawaharlal Nehru University: Asha Sarangi, Lipika Ravichandran
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Delhi Confused me/Pixabay

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in India	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in India: An Introduction	7
2.2. <i>School, Educational Services and their Delivery Mechanisms</i>	10
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in India: An Introduction.....	15
3.2. <i>Fiscal Autonomy: Restraints and Limits</i>	18
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in India: An Introduction	23
4.2. <i>Decentralization and Democratic Governance</i>	27
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in India: An Introduction.....	31
5.2. <i>Local Governments and their Functioning</i>	33
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in India: An Introduction	40
6.2. <i>Sanitation Development</i>	43

People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in India: An Introduction

Asha Sarangi and Lipika Ravichandran, *Centre for Political Studies, Jawaharlal Nehru University*

In the context of urban local government, community participation started around the early 1970s when the Urban Basic Service Program was launched by the central government with assistance from UNICEF.¹⁷ Community participation was ensured for the implementation of projects and reduction of operational costs. There are various programs which involve people's participation. In rural local governance, *gram sabha* ensures public participation in terms of budgetary discussion and other infrastructural and service needs of the people. Urban local governance also makes people's participation an important aspect for service delivery. But people's participation in deliberative decision-making can be more clearly seen in rural than urban local governance through *gram sabhas* in every village.

The setting up of *gram sabha* at village level has strengthened the people's direct involvement in their affairs. *Gram sabha* is the lowest level in the hierarchy of rural self-government and has been set up in each village to discuss the grievances of the people. The *gram sabha* consists of all members of the village who are eligible to vote in elections. *Gram sabha* is empowered to look after all the developmental issues of a village and has a binding duty to discuss them in meetings to obtain consensus of its members. *Gram sabha* is recognized as the assembly of *panchayati raj*. All the members of the *panchayats* at the village intermediate and district levels are elected directly by the people, and this gives way to representative democracy.

Most states have constituted social audit units (SAU) under *gram sabha* to audit various schemes like the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act of 2005 (MGNREGA), the Mid-Day Meal Scheme, the public distribution system, or the *Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana* for the housing purposes.

In the first meeting of the *gram sabha* generally following issues are discussed.

- the annual statement of accounts;
- the report on the administration of the preceding financial year;
- the development and other programs proposed for the financial year;
- the last audit report.

In the meeting held in the last quarter of the year, the following issues are generally discussed:

- the statement of expenditure incurred during the year;
- the physical and financial programs taken during the year;

¹⁷ Shri H Ramachandran, 'Vision 2020. Governance and People's Participation' (2020) <https://niti.gov.in/planningcommission.gov.in/docs/reports/genrep/bkpap2020/15_bg2020.pdf>.

- proposals for any changes in the program;
- budget of the *panchayat* and tax proposals of the *panchayat*.

Rural people's participation can be further seen in the Water Users Associations, Joint Forest Management, Watershed Association, Village Education Committee. Urban local governance ensures people's participation in Resident Welfare Associations (RWAs) or Neighborhood User Groups (NUGs). Both urban and rural participation can be seen in Self-Help Groups (SHGs) - Micro Credit.

A number of programs that clearly bring out the interesting relationship between rural-urban dynamics are listed below:

- The 73rd Amendment Act has ensured the participation of people in development activities. People can participate in the local decision-making, monitoring and implementation of plans and rural development projects through *gram sabhas* and *panchayats*.
- The *gram sabha* through their elected representatives ensures a vivid participation for people in their various community development programs such as water and irrigation, roads, schools etc.
- Non-governmental organizations and civil society groups play an important role in the facilitation of participation by people for various developmental projects as well as rights-based acts such Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act of 2005 popularly known as MGNREGA.
- In MGNREGA, social audit over all the works covered under the act plays a powerful role for rural transformation and development. Moreover, it ensures steady participation of people and accountability on the side of the local government.
- Along with the Right to Information Act (RTI) of 2005, transparency and accountability have been ensured by the government to facilitate people's participation in the process of governance and decision-making.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

— — 'Building Capacities for Empowerment: The Missing Link Between Social Protection and Social Justice: Case of Social Audits in Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act in India' (Social Protection for Social Justice Conference, Brighton, April 2011)

Abbott J, *Sharing the City: Community Participation in Urban Management* (Routledge 2013)

Alam SM and Alam MN, 'Good Governance and Employment Generation through MGNREGA' (2014) 2 International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management 1

Breitkreuz R and others, 'The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme: A Policy Solution to Rural Poverty in India?' (2017) 35 Development Policy Review 397

Desai S, Vashishtha P and Joshi O, 'Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act: A Catalyst for Rural Transformation' (working paper no 7259, National Council of Applied Economic Research 2015)

Gaventa J and Valderrama C, 'Participation, Citizenship and Local Governance' (background note, Strengthening Participation in Local Governance Workshop, vol 21, University of Sussex 1999)

Haque T, 'Socio-Economic Impact of Implementation of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act in India' (2011) 41 Social Change 445

Vij N, 'Collaborative Governance: Analysing Social Audits in MGNREGA in India' (2011) 42 IDS Bulletin 28

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

